

A STUDY ON HOSTEL STUDY HOUR AMONG HOSTEL STUDENTS IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR

B. Baskar* & S. Senthamizhan**

* Assistant Professor, Department of MBA, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

** II Year Student, Department of Management Studies, Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College (Autonomous), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu

Cite This Article: B. Baskar & S. Senthamizhan, "A Study on Hostel Study Hour Among Hostel Students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 7, Issue 1, Page Number 65-68, 2022.

Abstract:

This qualitative study employed grounded theory to explore the impacts of hostel life on the behavior, and personality of the students. Sample consisted ten hostel students, five male and five female hostel students, and age range was twenty to twenty-five. Open ended questionnaire was constructed for in-depth interviews. Grounded theory was used to conceptualize the findings. Results revealed that hostels have great importance in the educational journey of DSEC college students. Hostel study expands the social circle of the hostel students, because hostel study is a combination of multicultural social group. The personality characteristics associated with the hostel students are such as they are considered to be confident, punctual, social, realistic, compromising, responsible, and sharp in many domains of life. During hostel stay, students learn to live with different types of individuals, and hostel study life also increases the students' level of patience. It prepares students to accept challenges in practical life. Individual differences are very common among the hostel roommates. Result of the study can help to improve quality of hostel services in Tamilnadu, which may increase student's hostel study life satisfaction.

Key Words: Hostel Study, Hostel Life, Education, Personality, Behavior.

Introduction:

Human personality is shaped by the experiences of life. When a child is born the family provides a protective environment for the child, at the beginning the interactions are limited latter social interactions increase, and the process of socialization starts. Which enable the individuals to become an effective member of a society, Human's lifestyle and personality are affected by his/her surroundings. Therefore, the social structure plays a vital role in the development of personality and behavior. Researchers have been conducted to high light the importance of the home environment, and the role of family members in the development of the children. Differences in child development start with the socioeconomic status of the family, biological endowment, and educational differences. These family differences make enduring changes in the personality of the children.

Statement of the Problem:

With the increasing need of Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College implement a learn system, and students Hostel Study Practices will be done to determine how students impacts changes. It has been observed that students are of the opinion that Hostel Study practices is of little or no significant effect on their academic performance, hence have taken it frivolous, some students who ought to take Study serious feels it's an opportunity for them to stay away from college. This mentality and other erroneous have made nonsense of the Hostel Study time performance. As a result of the fore mentioned problems and many others, students have either lost interest in the subjects or have missed years in their course of study. Also, students have either lost interest in the utilization of continuous assessment in motivating students' interest in learning Business Studies or have disregarded it.

Review of Literature:

Walker and Hamilton (1990): Purpose of Hostel Study Time is that can student's learning outcomes in every evening study hour- Cognitive, Affective, particularly with regard to knowledge and understanding (Easily clarify the doubts regarding the subject and It will reduce number of failures in examinations), problem solving and other higher order skills are have during the study time.

Wyman (2004): Hostel Study is beneficial for teachers, learners, educators and parents as being Guidance Oriented because it involves data collecting for a long period. It yields more correct data which stimulate teachers to modify their teaching methodology. (Group discussion are made in study hours and It increases the performance level of students) This may play a dynamic role in identifying the remediation areas of student's weakness if correctly secured in what happening in classroom. Learners' performance is assessed properly.

Prouty & George (2003): As a holistic approach hostel study hour in the hostel where majority of the college going students are given an opportunity to evening hostel study, the skills of students in classroom is

increased. Now many countries stress upon the success of each student or hostel study is considered a way to certify that all students must have an opportunity to succeed in college.

Singhalaukh (1979) found that motivation has positive relationship with school performance and achievement. High and low achievement motivated students differ significantly on achievement score.

Scope of Study:

- The study analyzes the measures taken by the college to improve the results.
- The study time motivates the students to activity participate in the academic level.
- To assess student satisfaction towards the basic study hour facilities provided to students by the college.
- Level of evening study time among the students in the college which leads for the effective performance measures.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study effectiveness of hostel study hours among hostellers in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College.
- To analyze the benefits of hostel study hours.

Research Methodology:

Research methodology is the specific procedures or techniques used to identify, select, process, and analyze information about a topic. In a research paper, the methodology section allows the reader to critically evaluate a study's overall validity and reliability.

Research Design:

A study was carried out with the descriptive type of research.

Sampling Technique:

Random sampling method is used for conducting the study. Population - 1567 Sample Size - 125

Method of Data Collection:

Primary data collection has been taken for this research study.

Primary Data:

Data was collected with the help of structure questionnaires from 125 students of the Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur.

Statistical Tools Used:

- Percentage Method
- Chi-square test
- Correlation

Limitation of the Study:

- The survey is based on the opinion of the students, which may be biased.
- The study on impact of hostel study hours in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur
- The study on impact of hostel study hour has to be completed within a specified period of time.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Respondent Study on Hostel Study Improve the Performance

S.No	Particular	No. of Respondents	Percent
1	Highly Satisfied	22	17.6
2	Satisfied	76	60.8
3	Neutral	26	20.8
4	Dissatisfied	1	0.8
5	Highly Dissatisfied	0	0
	Total	125	100

Interpretation:

From the above chart we found the result of respondents, 17.6% Of the respondents are having Highly Satisfied, 60.8% Of respondents are having Satisfied, 20.8% of respondents are having Neutral, 0.8% of respondents are having Dissatisfied and 0% of respondents are having Highly Dissatisfied

Correlation Method:

The Satisfaction Towards the Clarification of Doubt	27	30	40	21	07	125
Attitude of Staff Towards the Academic Result	41	46	15	15	08	125

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
27	41	729	1681	1107
30	46	900	2116	1380
40	15	1600	225	600

21	15	441	225	315
07	08	49	-	56
$\sum X=125$	$\sum Y=125$	$\sum X^2=3719$	$\sum Y^2=4247$	$\sum XY=3458$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n\sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{n(\sum X^2) - (\sum X)^2} \cdot \sqrt{n(\sum Y^2) - (\sum Y)^2}}$$

Answer: $r_{xy} = 0.8080$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between the Satisfaction towards the clarification of doubt and attitude of staff towards the academic result.

Chi-Square Analysis:

To Compare the Continuous Assessment Practices Understanding and Improving your Performance Position by using Chi-Square test

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relation between the Understand by Continuous Assessment.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1):

There is a significant relation between the Continuous Assessment Practices will be improving your Performance.

Chi-Square Test 1:

Grade	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Strongly Agree	18	17	4	1	0	41
Agree	5	12	15	10	4	46
Neutral	3	1	4	5	2	15
Disagree	1	0	6	3	2	15
Strongly Disagree	0	0	5	3	0	8
Total	27	30	40	21	07	125

Calculations:

Chi-Square Test Formula: $X^2 = \sum (O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$

O_i = Observed Frequency E_i = Expected Frequency

O_i	E_i	$(O_i - E_i)$	$(O_i - E_i)^2$	$(O_i - E_i)^2 / E_i$
20	6.336	13.664	186.70	29.46
9	8.316	0.684	0.467	0.056
4	7.92	-3.92	15.366	1.940
0	6.6	-6.6	43.56	6.6
0	3.828	-3.828	14.653	3.827
22	20.352	1.648	2.715	0.133
30	26.712	3.288	10.81	0.404
25	25.44	-0.44	0.193	0.007
17	21.2	-4.2	17.64	0.832
12	12.296	-0.296	0.087	0.007
6	11.712	-5.712	32.62	2.785
4	15.372	-11.372	129.32	2.412
24	14.64	9.36	87.60	5.983
15	12.2	2.8	7.84	4.642
12	7.076	4.924	24.24	3.425
0	8.832	-8.832	78.00	2.123
20	11.592	8.408	70.69	6.098
5	11.04	-6.04	36.48	3.304
17	9.2	7.8	60.84	6.57
4	5.336	-1.336	1.784	0.334
0	0.768	-0.768	0.589	0.766
0	1.008	-1.008	1.016	1.007
2	0.96	1.04	1.08	1.125
1	0.8	0.2	0.04	0.05
1	0.464	0.536	0.287	0.618
Total				87.508

Level of significance= 5%

Degree of freedom in this case is 12

Calculated value = 87.508

Table value = 12.9. The calculated value is greater than the table value. So, we are rejecting the null hypothesis

Inference:

Since $X^2 > X^2_{0.05}$. So Null Hypothesis is rejected.

Suggestion:

Avoid using the mobile phone particularly in study hours. If you don't understand something, Ask Questions to your hostel warden. There is no combine study, so does that. If there is not homework, Make fast & well writing practice in hostel study hours. Do the Daily studies work. Study & Learn to Express Yourself Clearly in study hours.

Conclusion:

The study explored the impact of hostel study on hostel students. It highlighted the experiences, behavioral changes, and personality characteristics of the hostel students. It also studies the gender differences among the roommates. Results show that male hostel students are more prone to affect negatively during hostel stay as most of them indulge in drug addiction. Female hostel students adjust in hostel more easily than male students. Positive behavioral changes involved character building and preparing students for future practical life. The negative behavioral adaptations included students become lazy, show careless attitude toward studies, wasting time with friends, smoking and drug addiction in male students. Personality characteristics related with hostel students are as such they considered to be realistic, punctual, disciplined, independent, compromising, and well organized in hostel study hour.

References:

1. <https://www.educaremi.com/10-ways-to-improve-your-academic-performance/>
2. <http://www.interestjournals.org/ER>
3. www.learningstudyinginstitute.org
4. www.link.springer.com